

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D2.3 Questionnaire and Parameters

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ACRONYMS LIST:

EU:	European Union
Q:	Question
SQ:	Statistical Question

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a report on the design of the questionnaire and the standardization of the parameters resultant from the questionnaire. Firstly, the questionnaire is aimed at collecting all relevant information provided by the user of the mobile app, according to its specific needs. Secondly, the standardization of parameters is aimed at matching the decision tree and tags introduced in RightsApp Deliverable D2.2 “Decision Tree and particle tagged”.

Thus, this deliverable shows the questionnaire in four languages (English, Spanish, Portuguese and Italian), and the parameters of its implementation.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The RightsApp Deliverable D2.3 “Questionnaire and parameters” introduces the questionnaire in the four languages (English, Spanish, Portuguese and Italian) that will be included into the RightsApp mobile app, and the resulting parameters that will store the responses from the user. Both questionnaire and parameters work jointly with the decision tree and the tagged particles from RightsApp Deliverable D2.2 “Decision tree and tagged Particles”.

This document is an open document. It means that throughout the project it can be updated, especially after the validation stages planned in WP3 and WP4. For instance, the questionnaire can be modified to include more questions or to adapt the existing ones. Thus, this deliverable contains a revision log table. When relevant updates occur, the revision log table will reflect the update, the date of the new revision, and the author.

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 lists the questionnaire in four different languages, including questions and potential answers with their corresponding identification code. Finally, Section 3 introduces the parameters that will store the questionnaire results.

2 QUESTIONNAIRE

This Section offers the questionnaire in four different languages (English, Spanish, Portuguese and Italian). Each question has an ID that identifies it uniquely. Annex I contains the repository of questions sorted by their ID. On top of that, questions are divided into two different groups: i) Questions (Q) which collect relevant information (represented through the parameters discussed in Section 3) to provide the suitable particles¹ to the users of the mobile app; and ii) Statistical Questions (SQ) which collect information about the user for statistical purposes (however, answers to these SQ questions do not affect the workflow of the questionnaire).

The Spanish legal framework² grants additional rights when a citizen falls victim to a crime related to: terrorism, violence against women, violence or a crime against sexual freedom (specific crimes). Therefore, one of the main goals of the questionnaire is to find whether the citizen has suffered one of the specific crimes mentioned above. Moreover, the Spanish legal framework also considers specific and additional rights if the victim is direct or indirect or even if the victim is resident in another EU Member State. On top of that, it is also relevant whether the citizen requires information about the judicial procedure. All these conditions will tailor the provided particles. To sum up, the main goal of the questionnaire is to find which set of particles (tags)³ will be displayed to the user.

The questionnaire for each language in this Section is represented on four different tables. The first table is for Q1, this question picks one of the three available paths for the questionnaire: i) direct victim⁴; ii) indirect victim⁵; and iii) user looking for information⁶.

The second table lists the questions (Q and SQ) for direct victims. The third table shows the questions for indirect victims, and the fourth table is on users looking for information. It is worth noting that some questions appear in more than one path; for instance, SQ3 appears in all paths in different order. Some questions are basically the same, but we have changed their focus. For instance, Q2 and Q9 are the same question but they change the 2nd person of the singular (Are you resident in Spain?) for the 3rd person of the singular (Is the victim resident in Spain?). Thus, the questionnaire becomes more accurate and provides a better user experience in the answering.

2.1 Questionnaire in English

Table 1 shows the first question (Q1) of the questionnaire in English.

ID	Question	Answers
Q1	Have you been victim of a crime?	a) Yes, I have been victim of a crime

¹ Minimal and standalone pieces of information translated to a non-legal/non-technical language related to citizens' rights when they fall victim of a crime (see RightsApp Deliverable D2.2 "Decision Tree and particles tagged" for further information).

² Based on the work introduced in RightsApp Deliverable D2.1 "Report on key sources for the project".

³ For further information about particles, tags and the decision tree, see RightsApp Deliverable D2.2 "Decision Tree and particles tagged".

⁴ The individual that suffers the harm or the damage.

⁵ The indirect victim is the victim suffering the consequences of a crime committed against a relative, resulting in death, disappearance or, temporal or permanent disability for the relative. The Spanish legal framework recognizes some specific rights to indirect victims.

⁶ This path is specific for the citizen looking for information for a relative or acquittance. Essentially, the path is like the direct victim's one, but the questions are rephrased to focus on a third individual.

		<p>b) Yes, I am suffering the consequences of a crime committed against a relative (resulting in death, disappearance or, temporal or permanent disability)</p> <p>c) No, I am looking for information for a relative or acquaintance</p>
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Table 1: Questionnaire in English, first question

Table 2 lists the questions in English for the questionnaire when the path is for direct victims. Do notice that some questions will be only shown taking into account the answer to previous questions. For instance, if the answer to Q2 is “Yes”, there is no need to proceed with Q3, thus, Q3 will be skipped. The RightsApp Deliverable D2.2 “Decision Tree and particles tagged” contains the different paths and workflows.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	How old are you?	<p>a) Less than 18 years old</p> <p>b) Between 18 and 25 years old</p> <p>c) Between 26 and 35 years old</p> <p>d) Between 36 and 45 years old</p> <p>e) Between 46 and 55 years old</p> <p>f) Between 56 and 65 years old</p> <p>g) More than 65 years old</p>
SQ2	Are you a man or a woman?	<p>a) Man</p> <p>b) Woman</p>
Q2	Are you resident in Spain?	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p>
Q3	Are you resident in a EU Member State?	<p>a) Yes</p> <p>b) No</p>
Q4	What happened?	<p>a) Wallet or Bag Theft</p> <p>b) Threats or intimidation (off line/online)</p> <p>c) Mobile devices theft (telephone, tablet, laptop computer, others)</p> <p>d) Snatching</p> <p>e) Assault</p> <p>f) Minor physical or psychological damages</p> <p>g) Computer related crimes</p> <p>h) Vehicle theft</p> <p>i) Theft of vehicle accessories or inside a vehicle</p> <p>j) Burglary, breaking and entering</p> <p>k) Others</p>
SQ3	Where did it happen?	<p>a) Public road</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) Place (Hotel, store, pub, club, working facilities, school, college, garage, etc.) c) Public or private transport (underground, bus, taxi, owned or shared car, etc.) d) House e) Other places f) Do not know / Do not answer
Q5	Have you been victim of a crime that involves violence against women? (Offenses committed by a man against a woman with whom he has a relationship. It involves an act of physical or psychic violence against women to force their will. It includes abuse, aggression or sexual harassment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q6	Have you been victim of a terrorist attack?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q7	Have you been victim of a violent or sexual crime? (Serious injuries or damages affecting the victim's physical integrity or physical and mental health and disabling her temporarily or permanently)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q8	Do you want to receive information about victim's rights related to the criminal process?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No

Table 2: Questionnaire in English for direct victims

Table 3 lists the questions in English for the questionnaire when the path is for indirect victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	How old are you?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Less than 18 years old b) Between 18 and 25 years old c) Between 26 and 35 years old d) Between 36 and 45 years old e) Between 46 and 55 years old f) Between 56 and 65 years old g) More than 65 years old
SQ2	Are you man or woman?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Man b) Woman
Q2	Are you resident in Spain?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No

Q3	Are you resident in a EU Member State?	a) Yes b) No
Q12	Did the victim suffered a crime that involves violence against women? (Offenses committed by a man against a woman with whom he has a relationship. It involves an act of physical or psychic violence against women to force their will. It includes abuse, aggression or sexual harassment)	a) Yes b) No
Q13	Did the victim suffer a terrorist attack?	a) Yes b) No
Q14	Did the victim suffer a violent or sexual crime? (Serious injuries or damages affecting the victim’s physical integrity or physical and mental health and disabling her temporarily or permanently)	a) Yes b) No
SQ3	Where did it happen?	a) Public road b) Place (Hotel, store, pub, club, working facilities, school, college, garage, etc.) c) Public or private transport (underground, bus, taxi, owned or shared car, etc.) d) House e) Other places f) Do not know / Do not answer
Q8	Do you want to receive information about victim’s rights related to the criminal process?	a) Yes b) No

Table 3: Questionnaire in English for indirect victims

Table 4 lists the questions in English for the questionnaire when the path is for a user looking for information.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ4	How old is the victim?	a) Less than 18 years old b) Between 18 and 25 years old c) Between 26 and 35 years old d) Between 36 and 45 years old e) Between 46 and 55 years old f) Between 56 and 65 years old g) More than 65 years old
SQ5	Is the victim man or woman?	a) Man

		b) Woman
Q9	Is the victim resident in Spain?	a) Yes b) No
Q10	Is the victim resident in a EU Member State?	a) Yes b) No
Q11	What happened to the victim?	a) Wallet or Bag Theft b) Threats or intimidation (off line/online) c) Mobile devices theft (telephone, tablet, laptop computer, others) d) Snatching e) Assault f) Minor physical or psychological damages g) Computer related crimes h) Vehicle theft i) Theft of vehicle accessories or inside a vehicle j) Burglary, breaking and entering k) Others
SQ3	Where did it happen?	a) Public road b) Place (Hotel, store, pub, club, working facilities, school, college, garage, etc.) c) Public or private transport (metro, bus, taxi, owned or shared car, etc.) d) House e) Other places f) Do not know / Do not answer
Q12	Did the victim suffered a crime that involves violence against women? (Offenses committed by a man against a woman with whom he has a relationship. It involves an act of physical or psychic violence against women to force their will. It includes abuse, aggression or sexual harassment)	a) Yes b) No
Q13	Did the victim suffer a terrorist attack?	a) Yes b) No
Q14	Did the victim suffer a violent or sexual crime? (Serious injuries or damages affecting the victim's physical integrity or physical and mental health and disabling her temporarily or permanently)	a) Yes b) No

Q8	Do you want to receive information about victim's rights related to the criminal process?	a) Yes b) No
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Table 4: Questionnaire in English for users looking for information

2.2 Questionnaire in Spanish

This Section shows the questionnaire in Spanish following the same structure as in the previous Section. Table 5 shows Q1 in Spanish for the questionnaire when the path is for direct victims.

ID	Question	Answers
Q1	¿Has sido víctima de un delito?	a) Sí, yo he sido víctima de un delito b) Sí, estoy sufriendo las consecuencias de un delito cometido contra un familiar (con resultado de muerte, desaparición o incapacidad permanente o temporal) c) No, busco información para un familiar o conocido

Table 5: Questionnaire in Spanish, first question

Table 6 lists the questions in Spanish for the questionnaire when the path is for direct victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	¿Qué edad tienes?	a) Menor de 18 años b) Entre 18 y 25 años c) Entre 26 y 35 años d) Entre 36 y 45 años e) Entre 46 y 55 años f) Entre 56 y 65 años g) Más de 65 años
SQ2	¿Eres hombre o mujer?	a) Hombre b) Mujer
Q2	¿Eres residente en España?	a) Sí b) No
Q3	¿Eres residente en un país miembro de la UE?	a) Sí b) No
Q4	¿Qué te ha ocurrido?	a) Robo de bolsa o cartera b) Amenazas o intimidaciones (online o offline) c) Robo de dispositivo móvil (teléfono, tableta, portátil, otros) d) Tirón e) Atraco f) Agresiones físicas g) Robo accesorios de coche h) Robo de objetos del interior del vehículo i) Robo de otros en el vehículo j) Robo en la vivienda k) Otros

SQ3	¿Dónde te ha ocurrido?	a) Vía pública b) Establecimiento (Hotel, tienda, discoteca, bar, trabajo, centro educativo, parque, etc.) c) Transporte público (metro, autobús, taxi, etc.) o privado (vehículo propio o compartido) d) Casa e) Otros espacios f) NS/NC
Q5	¿Has sido víctima de un delito de violencia de género? (Delitos que comete un hombre contra una mujer con la que mantiene una relación afectiva. Siempre implican un acto violento de fuerza física o psíquica contra la mujer para forzar su voluntad. Se incluyen abuso, agresión o acoso sexual)	a) Sí b) No
Q6	¿Has sido víctima de un delito de terrorismo? (Atentado)	a) Sí b) No
Q7	¿Has sido víctima de un delito violento o contra la libertad sexual? (Lesiones graves o daños que afecten a tu integridad corporal o salud física y mental y que incapaciten temporal o permanentemente)	a) Sí b) No
Q8	¿Quieres recibir información sobre los derechos de la víctima durante el proceso penal?	a) Sí b) No

Table 6: Questionnaire in Spanish for direct victims

Table 7 lists the questions in Spanish for the questionnaire when the path is for indirect victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	¿Qué edad tienes?	a) Menor de 18 años b) Entre 18 y 25 años c) Entre 26 y 35 años d) Entre 36 y 45 años e) Entre 46 y 55 años f) Entre 56 y 65 años g) Más de 65 años
SQ2	¿Eres hombre o mujer?	a) Hombre

		b) Mujer
Q2	¿Eres residente en España?	a) Sí b) No
Q3	¿Eres residente en un país miembro de la UE?	a) Sí b) No
Q12	¿Ha sido víctima de un delito de violencia de género? (Delitos que comete un hombre contra una mujer con la que mantiene una relación afectiva. Siempre implican un acto violento de fuerza física o psíquica contra la mujer para forzar su voluntad. Se incluyen abuso, agresión o acoso sexual)	a) Sí b) No
Q13	¿Ha sido víctima de un delito de terrorismo? (Atentado)	a) Sí b) No
Q14	¿Ha sido víctima de un delito violento o contra la libertad sexual? (Lesiones graves o daños que afecten a tu integridad corporal o salud física y mental y que incapaciten temporal o permanentemente)	a) Sí b) No
SQ3	¿Dónde te ha ocurrido?	a) Vía pública b) Establecimiento (Hotel, tienda, discoteca, bar, trabajo, centro educativo, parquin, etc.) c) Transporte público (metro, autobús, taxi, etc.) o privado (vehículo propio o compartido) d) Casa e) Otros espacios f) NS/NC
Q8	¿Quieres recibir información sobre los derechos de la víctima durante el proceso penal?	a) Sí b) No

Table 7: Questionnaire in Spanish for indirect victims

Table 8 lists the questions in Spanish for the questionnaire when the path is for a user looking for information.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ4	¿Qué edad tiene la víctima?	a) Menor de 18 años

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) Entre 18 y 25 años c) Entre 26 y 35 años d) Entre 36 y 45 años e) Entre 46 y 55 años f) Entre 56 y 65 años g) Más de 65 años
SQ5	¿La víctima es hombre o mujer?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Hombre b) Mujer
Q9	¿Es residente en España?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sí b) No
Q10	¿Es residente en un país miembro de la UE?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sí b) No
Q11	¿Qué le ha ocurrido?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Robo de bolsa o cartera b) Amenazas o intimidaciones (online o offline) c) Robo de dispositivo móvil (teléfono, tableta, portátil, otros) d) Tirón e) Atraco f) Agresiones físicas g) Robo accesorios de coche h) Robo de objetos del interior del vehículo i) Robo de otros en el vehículo j) Robo en la vivienda k) Otros
SQ3	¿Dónde le ha ocurrido?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Vía pública b) Establecimiento (Hotel, tienda, discoteca, bar, trabajo, centro educativo, parquin, etc.) c) Transporte público (metro, autobús, taxi, etc.) o privado (vehículo propio o compartido) d) Casa e) Otros espacios f) NS/NC
Q12	¿Ha sido víctima de un delito de violencia de género? (Delitos que comete un hombre contra una mujer con la que mantiene una relación afectiva. Siempre implican un acto violento de fuerza física o psíquica contra la mujer para forzar su voluntad.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sí b) No

	Se incluyen abuso, agresión o acoso sexual)	
Q13	¿Ha sido víctima de un delito de terrorismo? (Atentado)	a) Sí b) No
Q14	¿Ha sido víctima de un delito violento o contra la libertad sexual? (Lesiones graves o daños que afecten a tu integridad corporal o salud física y mental y que incapaciten temporal o permanentemente)	a) Sí b) No
Q8	¿Quieres recibir información sobre los derechos de la víctima durante el proceso penal?	a) Sí b) No

Table 8: Questionnaire in Spanish for a user looking for information

2.3 Questionnaire in Portuguese

Table 9 shows the first question (Q1) of the questionnaire in Portuguese.

ID	Question	Answers
Q1	Você foi vítima de um crime?	a) Sim, eu fui vítima de um crime b) Sim, estou sofrendo as conseqüências de uma ofensa cometida contra um parente (resultando em morte, desaparecimento ou invalidez permanente ou temporária) c) Não, estou procurando informações para um membro da família ou conhecido

Table 9: Questionnaire in Portuguese, first question

Table 10 lists the questions in Portuguese for the questionnaire when the path is for direct victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	Quantos anos tens?	a) Menores de 18 anos b) Entre 18 e 25 anos c) Entre 26 e 35 anos d) Entre 36 e 45 anos e) Entre 46 e 55 anos f) Entre 56 e 65 anos g) Mais de 65 anos
SQ2	Você é homem ou mulher?	a) Homem b) Mulher
Q2	Você é um residente da Espanha?	a) Sim b) Não
Q3	Você é um residente de um país da UE?	a) Sim b) Não
Q4	O que aconteceu com você?	a) Roubo de bolsa ou carteira b) Ameaças e intimidações (off-line/on-line) c) Roubo de dispositivo móvel (telefone, tablet, laptop, outros) d) Assalto e) Lesões físicas ou psíquicas menores f) Criminalidade informática g) Roubo de veículo h) Roubo de acessórios de veículos i) Roubo de objetos dentro do veículo k) Outros
SQ3	Onde isso aconteceu com você?	a) Via pública

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) Estabelecimento (Hotel, Loja, Discoteca, Bar, Lugar de trabalho, Estabelecimento de ensino, Parking...) c) Transporte público (Metrô, autocarro, trem, taxi) ou particular (coche, veículo compartilhado) d) Casa e) Outros lugares f) Não sabem ou não respondem
Q5	Você já foi vítima de um delito de violência contra as mulheres? (Crimes cometidos por um homem contra uma mulher com quem ele mantém um relacionamento afetivo. Eles sempre implicam um violento ato de força física ou psíquica contra as mulheres para forçar sua vontade. Incluem abuso, agressão ou assédio sexual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não
Q6	Você foi vítima de um crime terrorista? (ataque terrorista)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não
Q7	Você foi vítima de um crime violento ou contra a liberdade sexual? (Lesões graves ou danos que afetam a integridade física ou a saúde física e mental da vítima e que temporária ou permanentemente incapacitam a vítima do crime)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não
Q8	Você deseja receber informações sobre os direitos da vítima durante o processo criminal?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não

Table 10: Questionnaire in Portuguese for direct victims

Table 11 lists the questions in Portuguese for the questionnaire when the path is for indirect victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	Quantos anos tens?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Menores de 18 anos b) Entre 18 e 25 anos c) Entre 26 e 35 anos d) Entre 36 e 45 anos e) Entre 46 e 55 anos f) Entre 56 e 65 anos g) Mais de 65 anos
SQ2	Você é homem ou mulher?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Homem

		b) Mulher
Q2	Você é um residente da Espanha?	a) Sim b) Não
Q3	Você é um residente de um país da UE?	a) Sim b) Não
Q12	A vítima sofreu um delito de violência contra as mulheres? (Crimes cometidos por um homem contra uma mulher com quem ele mantém um relacionamento afetivo. Eles sempre implicam um violento ato de força física ou psíquica contra as mulheres para forçar sua vontade. Incluem abuso, agressão ou assédio sexual)	a) Sim b) Não
Q13	A vítima sofreu um crime terrorista? (ataque terrorista)?	a) Sim b) Não
Q14	A vítima sofreu um crime violento ou contra a liberdade sexual? (Lesões graves ou danos que afetam a integridade física ou a saúde física e mental da vítima e que temporária ou permanentemente incapacitam a vítima do crime)	a) Sim b) Não
SQ3	Onde isso aconteceu com você?	a) Via pública b) Estabelecimento (Hotel, Loja, Discoteca, Bar, Lugar de trabalho, Estabelecimento de ensino, Parking...) c) Transporte público (Metrô, autocarro, trem, taxi) ou particular (coche, veículo compartilhado) d) Casa e) Outros lugares f) Não sabem ou não respondem
Q8	Você deseja receber informações sobre os direitos da vítima durante o processo criminal?	a) Sim b) Não

Table 11: Questionnaire in Portuguese for indirect victims

Table 12 lists the questions in Portuguese for the questionnaire when the path is for a user looking for information.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ4	Quantos anos tem a vítima?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Menores de 18 anos b) Entre 18 e 25 anos c) Entre 26 e 35 anos d) Entre 36 e 45 anos e) Entre 46 e 55 anos f) Entre 56 e 65 anos g) Mais de 65 anos
SQ5	A vítima é um homem ou uma mulher?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Homem b) Mulher
Q9	A vítima é residente da Espanha?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não
Q10	A vítima é residente de un país da UE?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não
Q11	O que aconteceu com a vítima?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Roubo de bolsa ou carteira b) Ameaças e intimidações (off-line/on-line) c) Roubo de dispositivo móvel (telefone, tablet, laptop, outros) d) Assalto e) Lesões físicas ou psíquicas menores f) Criminalidade informática g) Roubo de veículo h) Roubo de acessórios de veículos i) Roubo de objetos dentro do veículo k) Outros
SQ3	Onde isso aconteceu?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Via pública b) Estabelecimento (Hotel, loja, discoteca, bar, lugar de trabalho, estabelecimento de ensino, parking, etc.) c) Transporte público (Metrô, autocarro, trem, taxi) ou particular (coche, veículo compartilhado) d) Casa e) Outros lugares f) Não sabem ou não respondem
Q12	A vítima sofreu um delito de violência contra as mulheres? (Crimes cometidos por um homem contra uma mulher com quem ele mantém um relacionamento afetivo. Eles sempre implicam um violento ato de força física ou psíquica contra as mulheres para forçar sua	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sim b) Não

	vontade. Incluem abuso, agressão ou assédio sexual)	
Q13	A vítima sofreu um crime terrorista? (ataque terrorista)?	a) Sim b) Não
Q14	A vítima sofreu um crime violento ou contra a liberdade sexual? (Lesões graves ou danos que afetam a integridade física ou a saúde física e mental da vítima e que temporária ou permanentemente incapacitam a vítima do crime)	a) Sim b) Não
Q8	Você deseja receber informações sobre os direitos da vítima durante o processo criminal?	a) Sim b) Não

Table 12: Questionnaire in Portuguese for a user looking for information

2.4 Questionnaire in Italian

Table 13 shows the first question (Q1) of the questionnaire in Italian.

ID	Question	Answers
Q1	Sei stato vittima di un crimine?	a) Sì, sono stato vittima di un crimine b) Sì, sto subendo le conseguenze di un reato commesso contro un parente (risultante in morte, scomparsa o invalidità permanente o temporanea) c) No, sto cercando informazioni per un familiare o un conoscente

Table 13: Questionnaire in Italian, first question

Table 14 lists the questions in Italian for the questionnaire when the path is for direct victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	Quanti anni hai?	a) Sotto i 18 anni b) Tra 18 e 25 anni c) Tra 26 e 35 anni d) Tra 36 e 45 anni e) Tra 46 e 55 anni f) Tra 56 e 65 anni g) Più di 65 anni
SQ2	Sei un uomo o una donna?	a) Uomo b) Donna
Q2	Sei residente in Spagna?	a) Sì b) Non
Q3	Sei residente in un paese dell'UE??	a) Sì b) Non
Q4	Cosa ti è successo?	a) Furto di borsa o portafoglio b) Minacce e intimidazioni (in linea/non in linea) c) Furto del dispositivo mobile (telefono, tablet, laptop, altro) d) Rapina e) Minori danni fisici e psicologici f) Crimini informatici g) Furto del veicolo h) Furto di accessori per auto i) Furto di oggetti all'interno del veicolo k) Altri
SQ3	Dove ti è successo?	a) Vía pubblica

		b) Posto (Albergo, Negozio, Discoteca, Bar, Luogo di lavoro, Scuola, Liceo, Parcheggio, eccetera) c) Trasporti pubblici (metropolitana, autobus, taxi, tram, treno, eccetera) o privato (propria auto, auto in condivisione) d) Casa e) Altrove f) NS/NC
Q5	Sei stato vittima di un crimine di violenza contro le donne? (Delitti commessi da un uomo contro una donna con la quale intrattiene una relazione affettiva. Esse implicano sempre un atto violento di forza fisica o psichica nei confronti delle donne per forzare la loro volontà. Includono abuso, aggressività o molestie sessuali)	a) Sì b) Non
Q6	Sei stato vittima di un crimine terrorista? (Attentato)	a) Sì b) Non
Q7	Sei stato vittima di un crimine violento o contro la libertà sessuale? (Lesioni gravi o danni che compromettono l'integrità fisica o fisica e mentale della vittima e che paralizzano temporaneamente o definitivamente la vittima del reato)	a) Sì b) Non
Q8	Vuoi ricevere informazioni sui diritti della vittima durante il processo criminale?	a) Sì b) Non

Table 14: Questionnaire in Italian for direct victims

Table 15 lists the questions in Italian for the questionnaire when the path is for indirect victims.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	Quanti anni hai?	a) Sotto i 18 anni b) Tra 18 e 25 anni c) Tra 26 e 35 anni d) Tra 36 e 45 anni e) Tra 46 e 55 anni f) Tra 56 e 65 anni g) Più di 65 anni
SQ2	Sei un uomo o una donna?	a) Uomo b) Donna

Q2	Sei residente in Spagna?	a) Sì b) Non
Q3	Sei residente in un paese dell'UE??	a) Sì b) Non
Q12	La vittima ha subito un crimine di violenza contro le donne? (Delitti commessi da un uomo contro una donna con la quale intrattiene una relazione affettiva. Esse implicano sempre un atto violento di forza fisica o psichica nei confronti delle donne per forzare la loro volontà. Includono abuso, aggressività o molestie sessuali)	a) Sì b) Non
Q13	La vittima ha subito un crimine terroristico? (Attentato)	a) Sì b) Non
Q14	La vittima ha subito un crimine violento o contro la libertà sessuale? (lesioni gravi o danni che compromettono l'integrità fisica o fisica e mentale della vittima e che paralizzano temporaneamente o definitivamente la vittima del reato)	a) Sì b) Non
SQ3	Dove ti è successo?	a) Via pubblica b) Posto (Albergo, Negozio, Discoteca, Bar, Luogo di lavoro, Scuola, Liceo, Parcheggio, eccetera) c) Trasporti pubblici (metropolitana, autobus, taxi ,tram, treno, eccetera) o privato (propria auto, auto in condivisione) d) Casa e) Altrove f) NS/NC
Q8	Vuoi ricevere informazioni sui diritti della vittima durante il processo criminale?	a) Sì b) Non

Table 15: Questionnaire in Italian for indirect victims

Table 16 lists the questions in Italian for the questionnaire when the path is for a user looking for information.

ID	Question	Answers
SQ4	Quanti anni ha la vittima?	a) Sotto i 18 anni b) Tra 18 e 25 anni

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Tra 26 e 35 anni d) Tra 36 e 45 anni e) Tra 46 e 55 anni f) Tra 56 e 65 anni g) Più di 65 anni
SQ5	La vittima è un uomo o una donna?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Uomo b) Donna
Q9	La vittima è residente in Spagna?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sì b) Non
Q10	La vittima è residente in un paese dell'UE?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sì b) Non
Q11	Cosa è successo alla vittima?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Furto di borsa o portafoglio b) Minacce e intimidazioni (in linea/non in linea) c) Furto del dispositivo mobile (telefono, tablet, laptop, altro) d) Rapina e) Minori danni fisici e psicologici f) Crimini informatici g) Furto del veicolo h) Furto di accessori per auto i) Furto di oggetti all'interno del veicolo k) Altri
SQ3	Dove è successo?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Via pubblica b) Posto (Albergo, Negozio, Discoteca, Bar, Luogo di lavoro, Scuola, Liceo, Parcheggio, eccetera) c) Trasporti pubblici (metropolitana, autobus, taxi ,tram, treno, eccetera) o privato (propria auto, auto in condivisione) d) Casa e) Altrove f) NS/NC
Q12	La vittima ha subito un crimine di violenza contra le donne? (Delitti commessi da un uomo contro una donna con la quale intrattiene una relazione affettiva. Esse implicano sempre un atto violento di forza fisica o psichica nei confronti delle donne per forzare la loro volontà. Includono abuso, aggressività o molestie sessuali)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sì b) Non

Q13	La vittima ha subito un crimine terrorista? (Attacco)	a) Sì b) Non
Q14	La vittima ha subito un crimine violento o contro la libertà sessuale? (lesioni gravi o danni che compromettono l'integrità fisica o fisica e mentale della vittima e che paralizzano temporaneamente o definitivamente la vittima del reato)	a) Sì b) Non
Q8	Vuoi ricevere informazioni sui diritti della vittima durante il processo criminale?	a) Sì b) Non

Table 16: Questionnaire in Italian for a user looking for information

3 PARAMETERS

The workflow of the questionnaire depends on the answers provided by the user. As a result, every run of the questionnaire will produce different sets of answers with different lengths, in this context, the length needs to be understood as the number of responses answered by the user. For this purpose, we introduce a vector in which every coordinate corresponds to a specific answer. Figure 1 (1) shows the vector where “ C_i ” means the answer to Question “ Q_i ” in a n -dimensional vector. Thus, every coordinate will be substituted by the proper Question or Statistical Question considered in the decision tree (Figure 1 (2), (3), (4), (5)).

According to this parametrization, the vector will contain the answers corresponding to the proper question designated by the decision tree. The answers will be represented in the vector as the position of the answer in the questionnaire, beginning in the 0. For instance, a 0 will represent that the citizen has answered a) in the questionnaire, 1 will represent the b) answer, and so on (see Figure 1 (6)).

- (1) $(C_0, C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_n)$
- (2) $(Q_1, C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_n)$
- (3) $(Q_1, SQ1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_n)$
- (4) $(Q_1, SQ1, SQ2, C_3, \dots, C_n)$
- (5) $(Q_1, SQ1, SQ2, Q_2, \dots, C_n)$
- (6) $(0, 1, 0, 0, \dots, C_n)$

Figure 1: Parameters from the Questionnaire.

Table 17 shows one example for each path of execution of the questionnaire.

Path	Questions/answers	Parameters
Direct victim	Q1-a; SQ1-b; SQ2-a; Q2-a; Q4-k; SQ3-a; Q5-a; Q8-a	(0,1,0,0,10,0,0,0)
Indirect victim	Q1-b; SQ1-6; SQ2-b; Q2-b; Q3-a; Q12-b; Q13-b; Q14-a; SQ3-b; Q8-a	(1,6,1,1,0,1,1,0,1,0)
User looking for information	Q1-c; SQ4-c; SQ5-a; Q9-a; Q11-c; SQ3-c; Q8-a	(2,2,0,0,2,2,0)

Table 17: Examples of the parameters stored for each possible path in the questionnaire

ANNEX I – QUESTIONS REPOSITORY IN ENGLISH

Questions repository in English:

ID	Question	Answers
Q1	Have you been victim of a crime?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes, I have been victim of the crime b) Yes, I am suffering the consequences of a crime committed against a relative (resulting in death, disappearance or, temporal or permanent disability) c) No, I am looking for information for a relative or acquaintance
Q2	Are you resident in Spain?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q3	Are you resident in a EU Member State?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q4	What happened?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Wallet or Bag Theft b) Threats or intimidation (off line/online) c) Mobile devices theft (telephone, tablet, laptop computer, others) d) Snatching e) Assault f) Minor physical or psychological damages g) Computer related crimes h) Vehicle theft i) Theft of vehicle accessories or inside a vehicle j) Burglary, breaking and entering k) Others
Q5	Have you been victim of a crime that involves violence against women? (Offenses committed by a man against a woman with whom he has a relationship. It involves an act of physical or psychic violence against women to force their will. It includes abuse, aggression or sexual harassment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q6	Have you been victim of a terrorist attack?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No
Q7	Have you been victim of a violent or sexual crime? (Serious injuries or damages affecting the victim's physical integrity or physical and mental health)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Yes b) No

	and disabling her temporarily or permanently)	
Q8	Do you want to receive information about victim's rights related to the criminal process?	a) Yes b) No
Q9	Is the victim resident in Spain?	a) Yes b) No
Q10	Is the victim resident in a EU Member State?	a) Yes b) No
Q11	What happened to the victim?	a) Wallet or Bag Theft b) Threats or intimidation (off line/online) c) Mobile devices theft (telephone, tablet, laptop computer, others) d) Snatching e) Assault f) Minor physical or psychological damages g) Computer related crimes h) Vehicle theft i) Theft of vehicle accessories or inside a vehicle j) Burglary, breaking and entering k) Others
Q12	Did the victim suffered a crime that involves violence against women? (Offenses committed by a man against a woman with whom he has a relationship. It involves an act of physical or psychic violence against women to force their will. It includes abuse, aggression or sexual harassment)	a) Yes b) No
Q13	Did the victim suffer a terrorist attack?	a) Yes b) No
Q14	Did the victim suffer a violent or sexual crime? (Serious injuries or damages affecting the victim's physical integrity or physical and mental health and disabling her temporarily or permanently)	a) Yes b) No

Statistical questions repository in English:

ID	Question	Answers
SQ1	How old are you?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Less than 18 years old b) Between 18 and 25 years old c) Between 26 and 35 years old d) Between 36 and 45 years old e) Between 46 and 55 years old f) Between 56 and 65 years old g) More than 65 years old
SQ2	Are you man or woman?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Man b) Woman
SQ3	Where did it happen?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Public road b) Place (Hotel, store, pub, club, working facilities, school, college, garage, etc.) c) Public or private transport (underground, bus, taxi, owned or shared car, etc.) d) House e) Other places f) Do not know / Do not answer
SQ4	How old is the victim?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Less than 18 years old b) Between 18 and 25 years old c) Between 26 and 35 years old d) Between 36 and 45 years old e) Between 46 and 55 years old f) Between 56 and 65 years old g) More than 65 years old
SQ5	Is the victim man or woman?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Man b) Woman